

Moral Culture Means Moral Education

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Abstract: Culture — a certain level of historical development of society, human creative power and abilities. Moral culture is one of the factors influencing the development of society. It is necessary to analyze the place of the concepts of ethics and faith in scientific theory and society from a philosophical point of view. Moral culture should be resolved in the interpretation of moral education. A strong spirituality means a strong society.

Keywords: Ethics, manners, behavior, moral culture - moral education, behavior, behavior, standard, moral consciousness, moral feeling, emotion, attitude, behavior.

Ethical culture can be understood as the development of the concepts of etiquette, manners, and ethics at a high level. Etiquette includes beautiful behavior based on national traditions, which create a pleasant impression on a person, but are not so important in the life of the community, society and humanity. Behavior is a set of pleasant human behavior that is important at the level of family, community, neighborhood, but does not have a significant impact on society and human life. Morality is a set of positive actions that can serve as an example for society, time, and human history. Manners, manners, and morals come together from moral culture and moral education, and this shows the maturity of a person.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev chaired the video selector meeting held on January 19, 2021 on the issues of fundamental improvement of the system of spiritual and educational work and strengthening the cooperation of state and public organizations in this regard: "If society if the body of his life is economy, his soul and spirit is spirituality. As we decide to build a new Uzbekistan, we rely on two strong pillars. The first is a strong economy based on market principles. The second is a strong spirituality based on the rich heritage of our ancestors and national values," they acknowledged.

Ethical culture is a concept that reflects the high level of morality in society, the moral level of citizens. The full development of moral culture is firstly continued in the family, in pre-school education, in school education, in colleges and lyceums, in higher education, in further education and even in society. Ethical culture includes aspects such as a person's acquisition of the basic moral norms of society and his relationship with others on this basis, as well as regular self-improvement from the moral point of view. One of the most important factors of moral beliefs is behavior. In the process of communicating with each student, the pedagogue is motivated to follow moral standards and educate the student in the spirit of moral qualities. People cannot live without cooperation with each other, exchange of experience, and interaction. Therefore, communication and communication serve as a basic need and necessity for a person. Ethical upbringing of students in school education is considered a complex

process, and cooperation with parents and the community is started. We can see that the culture of treatment is formed through the culture of treatment. Etiquette requires respecting the dignity and respect of others, fulfilling traditional ethical and normative requirements. The teacher should be attentive not only in the process of communication, but also in the process of communicating with students in classes. Meaningful and fluent speech, ability to listen to the interlocutor, speech culture are important aspects of communication and this is reflected during the conversation. The best manners is the ability of a person to listen to the interlocutor. Language, which is the main means of communication, is of great importance in etiquette, and it is to express sweet words and meaningful thoughts. There is a wise saying in our people that "Both you" and "you" come out of the same mouth. Therefore, as an expression of respect for the interlocutor during communication, one should hear, listen, and then speak respectfully, taking into account the interlocutor's mood, interest and mood, taking into account his age, profession, social and family status, and not allowing inappropriate actions during the communication process. It is recommended to be especially careful when communicating with the student. Because children are brought up in different families, the pedagogue should start communication by feeling that there is a healthy family and an unhealthy family.

A person's gaze, gaze, non-verbal actions also play an important role in etiquette. It is known that a person's unspoken feelings and demands are reflected in his gaze, facial expression, and hand movements. That is why the primary school teacher needs to pay a lot of attention to this, because it is said that a primary school student is absorbed by his teacher, which means that the child takes all the actions and words from his teacher, imitates them. , is brought up like this. In this sense, it is noteworthy that people influence each other without giving advice or teaching manners. Moral maturity begins with the mastery of manners. Etiquette is a characteristic expression of moral culture. The word etiquette in French refers to the rules of etiquette of behavior formed in a certain society, accepted in a certain society. A pedagogue should have ethics, aesthetics, and behavior culture.

Ethical culture shows only the same regulated behavior for a particular situation. Therefore, the behavior of the pedagogue should be positive and effective. The scope of moral culture is so wide that it includes from simple human relations to internationally accepted rules of behavior. For example, the etiquette of a political figure, the ethical culture of hospitality, the etiquette of a host, etc., are formed when a person finds his place in society. Along with modern forms of moral culture, there are also national-traditional forms, without which it is difficult to imagine the life of any nation. For example, let's take greeting etiquette. There is a saying that greeting etiquette is the beginning of morality. According to the rules of moral culture, a person passing by on the street should greet the people standing in the street or in front of the gate, in this posture the right hand should be on the left breast, above the heart, and the head should be bowed slightly. In the culture of seeing, waving the hand indicates rudeness and disdain towards the person you are seeing.

In the process of education, students are taught that children should greet adults. We must explain that greeting is one of the national traditions of the Uzbek people. Through technology education, students learn national customs and traditions in the course of practical work. In the process of practical study of all types of work in the science of technology, students will improve their morals, morality, our traditions, and our nationality. As if there is no future without history, it is appropriate to always study and think about history. For example, they study the legacy of our great scholars, and learn by reading their dialogues in books and watching video films. Pupils will be educated spiritually by learning about our heritage, monuments, and history, which are worth the weight of gold left by the nation to the youth.

There is another aspect of moral culture: in it we can see the harmony of decency and beauty. That is, through moral culture, strict rules of etiquette are implemented through beautiful behavior. Professional etiquette is one of the highest forms of moral culture, and its place in

the life of society is incomparable. Professional manners such as teacher etiquette, artist etiquette, journalist etiquette, leadership etiquette are examples of this. Professional etiquette is a spiritual phenomenon manifested in the form of practical ethics, and is fully mastered in the science of technology.

Moral education is an important social event in the spiritual life of society, and it is a form of inculcating the moral system and moral qualities into the consciousness of each generation based on the requirements of the time. Moral education is a scientific category studied by literature, psychology, ethics and aesthetics. Every pedagogue should be accompanied by qualities such as ethics, aesthetics, manners, and morals. Moral education means a system of scientific and practical actions aimed at forming human qualities in the growing generation that correspond to the norms of behavior and meet the requirements of the time. A person's moral life is closely related to his moral education. It is necessary to educate students in the spirit of morality in every lesson, in every activity, especially in the family, the task of continuously forming the moral culture of preschoolers and schoolchildren and to be responsible in doing this it will be necessary.

The main task of moral sciences, i.e. pedagogy, psychology, ethics, aesthetics, and education, is to show the guidelines for educating a morally perfect person and society. Moral education is a continuous practical process on this path. It is not for nothing that the program of the 1-2-3-4 class of technology science is taught based on the requirements of the national program, because the development of society is reflected in nationalism. Through moral education, a person understands moral values, develops moral experiences, skills and qualities, learns to live on the basis of moral standards and principles. Moral education seeks answers to two important questions throughout human history: one is how to live, and the other is what to do and what not to do. There is a saying that the student gets what you teach and what you give, and it should be built on the basis of these positive qualities. Moral education is the way to perfection. There are many means of it, one is traditional education, the other is modern education. That is why the education of developed foreign countries was applied to us and we were given the task of organizing lessons in the spirit of national customs and traditions for the benefit of the people. The implementation of national education in the lessons increases nationalism and patriotism. Usually, both types of tools are used effectively. In school education, in moral education, fairy tales and narratives, teachings, traditional education in the spirit of games and toys are used in harmony with modern education.

Art is the most powerful tool of moral education. It covers all strata of the population - people of different ages and professions. The way of moral education that is relevant for all times is the principle of exemplification. It is desirable to combine moral education with mental-spiritual and physical education. Moral education of a person can be seen in his manners, compliance with etiquette rules, professional etiquette and all types of attitude towards others. Ethical relations - coordinate people's activities and express their noble, human relations. The structure of moral education consists of three main factors: moral awareness (moral awareness), moral feeling (moral feeling) and moral attitudes (moral behavior). In the process of moral education, these factors always participate together and demand each other. Concepts of moral education include such categories as goodness, duty, conscience, generosity, respect, honesty, purity, honesty. At the root of any moral decision made with the mind is a moral feeling.

In conclusion, moral education is effective if it is given from a young age in the family, school, other educational institutions and public places. There are sayings that education should start from the mother's womb and even that the mother should be educated. Technology plays an important role in the education of primary school students as a creative subject. Technological science is considered as an educational science in the spirit of national traditions and customs.

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